

Improving properties of recycled mortar aggregates of concrete using various binders

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ABSTRACT

In this paper it is proposed to improve the properties of construction demolition waste aggregates of concrete of mortar part by treating them with cement, lime, Alkali activated materials. The treated aggregates were cured as per binder requirements for 7 -28 days. The untreated and treated aggregates were tested for properties such as specific gravity, water absorption, Page impact test, crushing strength test. The improvement in parameters were evaluated.

Key words: Construction Demolition Waste Mortar aggregates, Lime, Cement, Alkali activated materials,

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INTRODUCTION

Sustainable construction is the use of recycling or reuse of the construction and demolition (C&D) waste to maintain a eco-friendly environment. The wide range of building materials and its compositions inhibit the efficient waste management and complete recycling after demolishing. Coarse recycled aggregates are made by crushing concrete, mortar, bricks. Mechanical and durability characteristics of Coarse Recycled Aggregate in concrete are less as compared to ordinary concrete., Recycled coarse aggregate (RCA) made from waste concrete is not a suitable structural material because of high absorption of cement mortar, which adheres on the aggregate surface and has tiny cracks thereon. Therefore, when using RCA made from waste concrete, increase of water content is suggested for concrete, and slump loss occurs when transporting. Hence, its workability is less than that of other materials. The strength of recycled concrete lower than that of conventional concrete by at least 10%. Hence there is dire need for improving the properties of the recycled aggregates. This paper evaluates the various methods and materials used in improving the properties of recycled aggregates with special emphasis on mortar aggregates.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Babar Ali, et al innovated usage of recycled nylon Fiber (RNF) to increase the ductility of high-performance concrete (HPC) made with Coarse Recycled Aggregates. The performance of CRA concrete can be augmented using different fibres and secondary binder materials. They found that RNF-based HPC provides a ductile, and eco-friendly alternative to an ordinary plain HPC.[1]

Chao-qiang Wang et al investigated the effects of two single and composite strengthening methods in Recycled aggregates(RA). A, mechanical vibration and acid solution immersion. The results showed that the composite strengthening method was more effective in augmenting the properties of RA. An increase in apparent density and bulk density by 5.59 % and 12.55 %, respectively, and a decrease in crush value and water absorption by 26.05 % and 15.52 %.[2]

A Sicakoval identified polymer emulsion treatment as the most effective way to improve RCA water absorption and Sodium silicate treatment to improve the compressive strength of concrete mixed with treated RCA.[3]

Eguchi K et al researched on, how adding recycled aggregates, by mixing them with other materials, impacts the concrete's strength, durability, and other properties.[4]

Ryou J et al in their study, coated the surface of recycled coarse aggregate with water-soluble polycarboxylate (PC) dispersant. RCA coated with PC dispersant was found to be better than crushed coarse aggregate and RCA when the physical properties of the fresh concrete and the mechanical, durability of the hardened concrete were tested.[5]

Tabsh studied the source of the recycled concrete and target concrete strength. The recycled coarse aggregate showed more loss than natural aggregate in toughness and soundness test.

The strength of recycled concrete was 10–25% lower than that of conventional concrete made with natural coarse aggregate.[6]

Choi H et al performed study on the mechanical performance, permeation resistance of concrete, and durability of surface-modified coarse aggregates (SMCA) produced using low-quality recycled coarse aggregates, the surface of which was modified using a fine inorganic powder. By coating the surface of the original coarse aggregate with surface-modification material, suppresses the occurrence of microcracks and improves the mechanical performance of the aggregate. The coating improved strength, permeability, and durability of concrete. [7]

Limbachiya et al study showed that up to 30% coarse RCA had no effect on concrete strength, but thereafter reduction in strength as the RCA content increased. [8]

Sago-Crentsil et al, study results showed that the performance of the concrete containing each type of Recycled Aggregate was influenced by the aggregate nature and quality, in addition to attached mortar content.[9]

Shayan et al, investigated on recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) in manufacture of nonstructural-grade concrete of up to 32 MPa-strength grade, The study involved improving the surface properties of RCA and report on the influence of the improved RCA on the strength development and durability properties of 50 MPa-strength grade concrete. Strength development, drying shrinkage, alkali-aggregate reaction (AAR), sulfate resistance, and chloride permeability were investigated. The results showed that RCA can be used to produce 50 MPa structural concrete with durability properties similar to concrete made with natural aggregate.[10]

Katz et al used aggregates from Concrete having a 28-day compressive strength of 28 MPa at ages 1, 3 and 28 days, mimicking the situation prevailing in precast concrete plants. The properties of the recycled aggregate and of the new concrete made from it, with nearly 100% of aggregate replacement, were tested. Significant differences were observed between the properties of the recycled aggregates of various particle size groups, while the crushing age had almost no effect. The properties of the concrete made with recycled aggregates were lesser than concrete made with virgin aggregates. [11]

Descarrega A et al tried to improve the recycled aggregates quality through surface treatment. different impregnation methods were developed for various origins and highly pozzolanic impregnation products. The rotating double impregnation test method was most effective. The increase of resistance was evaluated through the crushing factor test.[12]

Mistri A et al [13] reviewed the challenges in usage of CRA such as weak interfacial transition zone, high water absorption and presence of micro cracks. Methods of mitigation of these weaknesses through various treatments were also reviewed. They concluded that strengthening of attached mortar (AM) technique is better than removing of AM. Use of nano-materials and pozzolana along with different mixing methods and application of bio-cement is found to be better for developing the properties of recycled aggregates.[13]

Shaban reviewed different treatment methods of RCA treatments and analysed the strengths and weaknesses as well as the applicability and limitations of each method. [14]

Gupta A et al investigated the mechanical as well as micro structural properties of Recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) with uncoated and Geopolymer / Cement coated recycled aggregate exposed to elevated temperature. Test specimens were exposed to different levels of temperature (400°C, 600°C, 800°C) for a period of 6 hours in the muffle furnace. The reduction in compressive strength was observed are in the ranges from 23.4% to as high as 50.3% when exposed to different elevated temperature. [15]

Kou S et al, incorporated Class F fly ash in the concrete mix design to moderate the lower quality of recycled aggregates in concrete. They concluded that, to utilize a high percentage of recycled aggregate in concrete is by adding 25–35% of fly ash.[16]

Li J et al introduced a two-stage crushing process to produce recycled aggregate (RA). The slump of concrete mixes prepared by technique of stone enveloped with pozzolanic powder (SEPP) was compared with those using normal mixing approach (NMA) or stone enveloped with portland cement (SEPC) approach. The new mixing technique contributes significantly to better workability and higher compressive and flexural strengths. [17]

Li W investigated the effects of nanoparticles including nano-silica (NS) and nano-limestone (NL) on the crack propagation and microstructure properties of recycled aggregate concrete (RAC). The crack initiation and propagation of nanoparticles modified RAC with different nano-particle modification were evaluated using digital image correlation technique (DIC). The results showed that NS was more effective in augmenting the microstructure properties and improve the mechanical strength of RAC. [18]

Zhang H studied modification effects of a nano-silica slurry on properties of recycled aggregate concrete (RAC). The positive effects of the nano-silica slurry on RAC's mechanical properties were ascertained.[19]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lime is slaked lime obtained from local store generally used for white washing. Cement is Portland pozzolana cement obtained from local store. Alkali materials are obtained from scientific chemical supplier

Manufacturing of Mortar Aggregates

The 1-year-old M20 concrete cubes were broken and by hammer and mortar aggregates were separated by sieving through 12mm sieve and retained in 4.75mm sieve and by visual inspection.

Lime treatment

Select the sample of 3kg of aggregates. Prepare lime milk by mixing lime powder with water in the ratio of 1:5. Submerge the aggregates in lime milk for 7days. Cure the aggregates for 20 days by sprinkling water. Dry the aggregates for 2 days.

Cement treatment

Select the sample of 3kg of aggregates. Prepare cement milk by mixing Cement with water in the ratio of 1:5. Submerge the aggregates in cement milk for 1 hour as initial setting starts after 30 minutes and final setting time is near 6 hours. Cure the aggregates by soaking in water for minimum 7 days. Dry the aggregates for 2 days.

Alkali solution preparation

8 Mole Sodium Hydroxide (400gms in 1 litre) is mixed with sodium silicate in ratio of 1:2.5. Prepare a solution equivalent to 3 litres.

Alkali treatment

Select the sample of 3kg of aggregates. Soak the aggregates in the Alkali solution 1 day. Dry the aggregates for 5 days.

The treated mortar aggregates were tested as per Indian standard codes for specific gravity, water absorption, crushing strength and page impact.

Fig 1: Cement treated aggregates

Fig 2: Lime treated aggregates

Fig 3 : Alkali treated aggregates

TEST RESULTS

Mix	Specific gravity	Water absorption	Crushing strength	Page impact
Plain	2.38	10	38	35
Lime	2.39	7.5	38	36.7
Cement	2.4	5	31	26.7
AAM	2.56	5	30.5	20

Fig 4 : Specific gravity comparison of treated mortar aggregates

Fig 5 : Water absorption comparison of treated mortar aggregates

Fig 6 : Crushing strength comparison of treated mortar aggregates

Fig 7 : Page impact value comparison of treated mortar aggregates

Results and discussions

1. The specific gravity slightly increases with each treatment from lime, cement and maximum for AAM.
2. Water absorption of aggregates gets reduced with cement and AAM treated aggregates showing 50% reduction in water absorption
3. In crushing value test, Lime treated aggregates show values same as plain aggregates. Cement and AAM treated aggregates show percentage near 30.
4. The page impact values of Lime treated aggregates is more than plain aggregates. While cement and AAM treated aggregates show reduction in page impact values.

CONCLUSION

The natural aggregates used in concrete become recycled aggregates when concrete is crushed and recycled. The recycled aggregates show reduction in properties due to mortar adhering to the natural aggregates. Hence the weakest part of recycled aggregates i.e. mortar is used in this research as a source of recycled aggregates and treated using lime, cement and AAM. The

cement and AAM treatment increase the specific gravity and reduces the water absorption properties. The cement and AAM treatment reduce the crushing and page impact values, which is positive effect on impact and crushing resistance of mortar aggregates. By doing more indepth research and finetuning the materials and process we can certainly improve the properties of recycled aggregates.

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